

Research

Both Drug-Based and Nondrug-Based Ways to Deal with Body Pain Are Important Parts of Any Comprehensive Healthcare Plan

Dr. S M Mahamudul Hassan Rizvi^{1*}, Dr. Shengxiang Tao², Dr. Xiang Hu³, Dr. Liu Hui⁴, Dr. Shami. Aihemaiti⁵

Department of Orthopedic Trauma and Microsurgery, Zhongnan Hospital of Wuhan University, Wuhan 430071, China.

Abstract: Pain is a painful sensory and emotional experience associated with actual or potential tissue damage. Most patients report feeling discomfort, and their concern might be interpreted as a warning sign. An experience of the senses that produces anxiety and apprehension Distress may present itself in a variety of ways. It serves as a caution against physical injury, which is crucial for avoiding injuries and, ultimately, staying alive. Pain is the nervous system's warning signal when something is wrong. It's an uncomfortable feeling, like a pinprick, tingle, sting, burn, or ache. It's possible that the level of discomfort varies. It might be random, or it could be persistent.

Pain is the body's way of telling us that something is wrong with our tissues, such as an injury or a potential danger. The cause of this damage might be internal or external to the nervous system; it could be physical or chemical; and it could be obvious or subtle. Nonetheless, pain's basic role as the body's warning system stays unaltered regardless of the form it takes. A heightened sensitivity to pressure all over the body is a frequent symptom of the pain.

Keywords: Pain, Potential tissue damage, Sensitivity.

*Corresponding Author

Accepted: 23 February, 2023; **Published:** 20 March, 2023

How to cite this article: Dr. S M Mahamudul Hassan Rizvi, Dr. Shengxiang Tao, Dr. Xiang Hu, Dr. Liu Hui, Dr. Shami. Aihemaiti *Both Drug-Based and Nondrug-Based Ways to Deal with Body Pain Are Important Parts of Any Comprehensive Healthcare Plan.* North American Academic Research, 6(2), 188-210. doi: <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.7754081>

Conflicts of Interest: There are no conflicts to declare.

Publisher's Note: NAAR stays neutral about jurisdictional claims in published maps/image and institutional affiliations.

Copyright: ©2022 by the authors. Author(s) are fully responsible for the text, figure, data in this manuscript submitted for possible open access publication under the terms and conditions of the Creative Commons Attribution (CC BY) license (<https://creativecommons.org/licenses/by/4.0/>).

Introduction

Being in pain unintentionally may be upsetting for the person experiencing it and can have far-reaching effects on the person's life and the lives of those closest to them. Such discomfort might vary from mildly annoying to severely debilitating. Chronic pain is characterized by a prolonged period of discomfort and is often the result of a preexisting medical condition, such as arthritis, cancer, or fibromyalgia. What constitutes "pain" is subjective and might be defined differently by the patient, the physician, and the physiologist. In the eyes of the patient, the term connotes physical suffering and agony; in the eyes of the physician, it is a symptom; and in the eyes of the physiologist, it is an emotion that has its own unique neural system, beginning at the sensory receptors and ending in the brain. Chronic pain sufferers may experience unpleasant emotions such as grief and dread, and it is important to take these sentiments into consideration while deciding on a course of treatment even if the reason for their pain is unknown. Treatment of chronic pain must include both pharmaceutical and psychological approaches. Although it is a physical sense that may be proven using electrophysiological methods, feeling is, in theory, only an experience. The power and quality of a stimulus may be

affected by many different factors, both internal and external. This means that two people in the same environment may have vastly different experiences of the same stimulus.

One's perception of pain is very idiosyncratic, and it changes throughout the course of a single life. As people grow and gain new perspectives, their understanding of what constitutes fairness may evolve. The degree to which a person feels pain depends on a number of factors, including their current state of mind, the circumstances under which the pain was acquired, and whether or not the source of the pain is seen as a threat. It's not feasible to put a number on how much agony someone is in. It's possible that one's perception of pain is affected by factors such as arousal, focus, distraction, and environmental noise.

.[Domżał et al, 2007] [Thor P. et al, 2007], [Neural Plasticity and Disorders of the Nervous System. Cambridge University Press. Pain 2006.pp. 149–240.] [1]

Before we ever become aware of pain, our bodies go through a series of complex physiological reactions. It's crucial to go over unpleasant impulses in a matter of milliseconds. Acute pain alerts the body that danger is present or has already occurred, while persistent pain, such as that felt in a paralyzed limb that is not being used, may actually help the body recover. Sometimes, a single, very strong stimulus may make pain completely disappear without leaving any lasting effects. Repetitive stimulation of the central nervous system causes long-term potentiation (LTP) and other kinds of synaptic plasticity and changes in gene expression, which may either heighten or reduce the experience of pain. The opioids necessary for pain treatment are produced in the brain and spinal cord, which also activate various receptor systems that process signals for the creation of these chemicals. Also, these two locations are critical for the manufacture of molecules that alter how much pain is felt. The central nervous system, which includes the brain and spinal cord, produces opioid-like substances that help reduce the intensity of pain. Glial cells have been shown to play a crucial role in the outlined process. In certain cases, this complex procedure might cause discomfort to persist even after the underlying cause has been eliminated.[Helms J. Barone, 2008] [2]

The experience of pain is something that all of us can relate to. Although headaches are a common reason for people to visit the doctor, they are also one of the least well-understood and effectively treated issues. One possible explanation for this is that people's reactions to trauma, even when they've experienced the same thing, may differ greatly. In this piece, I'll go through the most common kinds of pain people experience and provide some suggestions on how to manage them most effectively. Since no one method can be assumed to work in every circumstance.[3]

Figure: General Body Pain.

Literature view

Pain:

A subjectively unpleasant sensation that might range from a little discomfort to a dull ache to searing agony. Some people report feeling pain in both their bodies and their minds. Pain is caused by the activation of nerve endings in the body. Injuries may cause localized pain, whereas systemic inflammatory disorders like rheumatoid arthritis can affect the whole body. This is usual for those who have chronic conditions like arthritis or fibromyalgia. Certain nerve fibers

transmit pain signals to the brain. These fibers may be found all throughout the body and are further classified as either A-delta fibers or C-fibers. where a number of factors may affect how those drives are seen in the here and now. [4]

Figure: General Neck Pain

General Information:

Patients with this illness often report feeling exhausted all the time and may also exhibit depressive symptoms. Humans feel pain because of nociceptors, which are nerves that sense tissue damage and send information about the injury to the brain through the spinal cord. For example, when you touch something hot, a signal is delivered from the spinal cord down a reflex arc, and your muscles contract instantly in response.

Patients should be asked to describe their pain in great detail, including its origin, intensity, duration, range of motion, sensory features, triggers, and relief mechanisms. By asking these questions and eliciting detailed descriptions of the patient's pain and other symptoms, medical professionals may get insight into the patient's condition and determine the most effective treatment. The Joint Commission updated its pain evaluation standards to give more weight to how the disease hinders patients' daily lives. [5]

Why is pain relief important?

Pain causes tremendous anguish for both patients and their loved ones, and it is difficult for anyone to feel in control of their health situation. Pain may cause an increase in blood pressure and heart rate, which can hinder healing. If the patient's pain can be controlled, they will feel better and perhaps recover more quickly. [5]

Purpose of pain assessment

In order to assist in diagnosis, it is helpful to be able to identify and precisely define the patient's pain. Knowing the source of the pain will allow you to choose the most effective treatment. You should monitor your pain to see whether the underlying ailment or sickness is improving or worsening and if the pain medication is helping. [6]

Classification of pain

Different kinds of pain are categorized according to how long they last and what causes them. Depending on how long the discomfort has been there,

Pain that lasts more than a week is considered chronic pain, whereas acute pain is defined as lasting less than a week.

Acute pain:

This kind of pain often develops after there has been evident damage done to the tissues, and as a result, it is of a nociceptive character. The source of the pain can be pinpointed, and it goes away after the wound has healed. Its main job is to give people clear and unmistakable warnings when there are situations that could be dangerous.

[Baumann, T.J et al. Pain Management.] [7]

Epidemiology

Introduction:

Consistently diagnosing and treating a patient with chronic pain may be challenging because pain is experienced differently by everyone and there isn't always agreement on diagnosis and illnesses in the medical profession. At the moment, it is hard to describe the epidemiology of pain, which makes it impossible to talk about proof that most pain problems really happen. [Henschke N et al. 2015][8]

It's not uncommon for people to feel pain in any of these, or all three, forms at once. Results of living with chronic pain include reduced mobility, less self-sufficiency, and a diminished standard of living, which is a multifaceted disorder including both biological and social/psychological aspects (QoL). It appears evident The field of public health must address the issue of pain treatment as a disease itself, [McGee SJ] et al. 2011 Sep;12[Tracey I and Bushnell MC, 2009 Nov;10] [9] instead of a mere side effect, in order to provide more effective pain management and avoidance.

Epidemiology:

As was previously said, data on pain occurrence are few. [Henschke N et al. 2015] Nevertheless, Tsang et al 2008's global epidemiology study reveals that The age-standardized prevalence of chronic pain issues in the previous 12 months is 37.3% in industrialized nations and 41.1% in developing countries, making the total prevalence of chronic pain problems 38.4%. [Tsang A et al. 2008 Oct;9] [10] The maps below illustrate the rough prevalence (in percentage terms) of a variety of painful conditions during the course of the previous year in a variety of countries, [Tsang A et al. 2008 Oct;9] [10] with data from the Tsang et al. 2008's report.

Estimated frequency of occurrence of pain conditions in the preceding 12 months is expressed as a percentage.

Estimated frequency of occurrence of pain conditions in the preceding 12 months is expressed as a percentage.

Point prevalence rates of neck discomfort were 3551.1% per 100,000 people in the standard age group, according to the 2017 Global Burden of Disease research. [Safiri S et al. 1990-2017] [11] Scandinavian countries including Norway, Finland, and Denmark have the greatest prevalence of neck discomfort. [Safiri S et al. 1990-2017] [11] Twenty percent of European adults have chronic pain, according to a 2006 research; however, just two percent of those with chronic pain ever seek treatment at one-third of people with chronic pain are not currently receiving treatment from a pain clinic. [Breivik H et al. 2006 May;10] [12] One-fifth of all individuals experience pain, and another one-tenth of a According to some estimates, one in every adult will get a diagnosis of chronic pain every single year. [13]

Symptoms:

Among the most typical manifestations of sudden pain are:

1. Sharp pain.
2. Throbbing.
3. Burning.
4. Stabbing pain.
5. Tingling.
6. Weakness.
7. Numbness. [14]

Figure: Indicators and manifestations of severe pain.

There are several types of acute pain. These are:

- Abdominal pain.
- Appendicitis.
- Back pain.
- Bites and stings. Breast abscess. Chest pain.
- Cold sores.
- Constipation [15]

Figure: Types of acute pain.

What is non-pharmacological pain management?

Pain may be managed in a number of ways, but one of them is non-pharmacological. This strategy makes use of mental retraining and concentrated attention to alleviate suffering. Education and psychological conditioning are two examples of non-pharmacological approaches to pain management.

It is highly distressing to go into cancer therapy without having any idea what to anticipate. Your degree of tension, on the other hand, will be much reduced if you are prepared and able to foresee what will occur. If you are informed, it will be easier for you to make crucial choices, speak about your alternatives with your doctor and caregiver, and converse with other individuals who have been through something similar to what you are going through.

The following may help relieve your mind throughout cancer treatment:

- Request a thorough walkthrough of the process, along with easy diagrams and photographs if possible.
- Have a sit-down with the individual who will be carrying out the operation, and jot down their responses to your questions.
- See the operating room before the surgery begins.
- Inquire as to the likely results of the procedure.

Hypnosis

During hypnosis, a psychiatrist or other medical professional will bring the patient into an altered state of consciousness. In this altered state, the patient is more receptive to suggestions and is able to direct their attention inward. This enables you to concentrate or restrict your attention in order to alleviate suffering and become more aware of the good parts of your life as well as the ways in which you might enhance your mental and physical health.

Methods for hypnosis include:

Imagery:

If you allow yourself to be led through made-up mental pictures of sights, sounds, tastes, smells, and sensations, it may be possible to redirect your attention away from the discomfort and toward the good feelings that are evoked by the images.

Distraction:

When helping children, particularly infants, distraction is often the method of choice. Preschoolers may be helped to deal with the discomfort of difficult medical procedures by using bright, moving items, watching a movie or a TV show, singing songs, or sharing stories. These activities can also serve as a distraction for preschoolers during uncomfortable medical procedures. Watching television or listening to music may be therapeutic for older children as well as adults. Make reasonable use of distractions, but do not substitute them for an explanation of what to anticipate. The use of distractions may be helpful, but caution is needed to ensure that they are used in the most effective manner.

Relaxation/guided imagery:

Many people find that following instructions for relaxation techniques like deep breathing and stretching may help them feel less uncomfortable and make it easier to manage their chronic pain.

Physical and occupational therapy, counseling, and psychological and social support, as well as companionship therapy, physical and occupational therapy, and neuro-stimulating therapies, are some examples of alternative therapies for non-pharmacological pain management. All of these approaches are geared toward reducing the amount of suffering that a person with chronic pain is enduring and boosting the amount of physical activity that they are able to engage in.

The following are some examples of strategies for managing pain that do not need the use of pharmaceuticals:

Comfort therapy

The following are some possible components of comfort therapy:

1. Companionship
2. Exercise.
3. Therapeutic use of cold and heat.
4. Compresses, rubs, and massages.
5. Meditation
6. Music, art, or drama therapy
7. Pastoral care and counseling.
8. Positioning

The following are examples of activities that may be included in physical and occupational therapy:

1. Aqua therapy
2. Tone and strengthening
3. Desensitization

Psychosocial therapy/counseling

The following are examples of possible components of psychosocial counseling and therapy:

1. Advice for One-On-One Situations.
2. Counseling for families.
3. Counseling in Small Groups.

Neuro stimulation

Neuro stimulation may involve the following:

1. Transcutaneous electrical nerve stimulation (TENS)
2. Acupuncture
3. Acupressure [16]

Pharmacological treatment:

Various classes of pain medicines exist, each with its own unique mechanism of action. The majority of drugs fall into one of three broad classes: non-opioids, opioids, or a hybrid of the two:

Nonopioids: medication that does not have structural similarities with morphine (an opioid) but also does not provide the same physiological effects.

Weak opioids: a drug with comparable effects to morphine (an opioid) but less of an opioid's "high" .

Combination opioids: the combination of a nonopioid with a low- or high-potency opioid (eg, acetaminophen and hydrocodone).

Strong opioids: medication with addictive potential, such morphine or others with comparable effects. Morphine and other opiates have a significant potential for misuse and dependency because of their strong addiction potential

Adjuvant treatments: medication that reduces inflammation or enhances the performance of other systems to alleviate pain Those who suffer from chronic pain may benefit greatly from the discovery of a treatment that might alleviate some of their symptoms (eg, cannabidiol, capsaicin cream, gabapentin).

Figure: Pharmacological pain management.

Acetaminophen or NSAIDs are the first line of treatment for mild pain; next comes a light opioid like codeine, dihydrocodeine, or tramadol; and ultimately, for moderate to severe pain, a powerful opioid like morphine (such as fentanyl, morphine, and oxycodone).

Modified Three-Step Pain Management Ladder

Different types of Acute Pain- Symptoms and Treatment:

Abdominal pain:

Abdominal discomfort may originate anywhere, from below the rib cage all the way down to the pelvis. Most cases of abdominal pain resolve without surgical intervention, and patients simply need to have their symptoms managed. You could also recognize it as discomfort in the belly or an upset stomach.

The abdomen houses your digestive system, liver, pancreas, small and large intestines, and reproductive organs. Numerous of your body's most important organs may be found in your abdomen, which helps you maintain health in many ways. The abdominal region is also home to many important blood vessel networks.

Appendicitis and complications during pregnancy are two serious causes of stomach discomfort. However, the majority of cases of stomach discomfort are not serious and resolve on their own. [17]

Manifestations of abdominal discomfort in adults

The origin of the pain may have a significant impact on the nature of the pain, which can severe, stabbing feeling. When one has stomach discomfort, it may:

- Can be described in a variety of ways, including sharp, dull, stabbing, cramping, twisting, etc.
- Can be fleeting, intermittent, or persistent.
- Can make throw up (vomit)
- Makes you either unable to sit still or so fidgety that you roam aimlessly until you reach "the correct posture."

It is possible to employ a three-step pain management ladder that has been updated to accommodate for the many kinds of pain people experience nowadays.

Causes of abdominal pain in adults

Abdominal discomfort may be caused by many different things. Appendicitis, gallstones, ulcers, infections, and complications during pregnancy are common causes of anxiety. These are just some of the numerous health issues that doctors fret about.

Occasionally, the source of abdominal discomfort is not the abdomen. heart attacks, pneumonia, pelvic In addition to the discomfort, you may also have difficulty urinating, having bowel movements, or having your period.

Because the organs and systems in the abdomen are so complicated, it is not always possible to make a final diagnosis. After asking a series of questions, the doctor will do a thorough examination. No more examinations are permitted by the doctor. Sometimes, it's obvious that the underlying issue causing the pain isn't catastrophic. It's also possible that the doctor is stumped, but the pain resolves on its own within a few hours to a few days. If surgery or hospitalization is necessary, the doctor will decide that.^[18]

Diagnosis of abdominal pain in adults

1. An inspection of the rectal cavity for signs of abnormality, such as blood.
2. Pregnancy testing in addition to a pelvic exam to look for issues with the uterus, fallopian tubes, and ovaries.
3. Infection (which generates an elevated white cell count) and bleeding may both be detected with a simple blood test (which causes a low blood count or hemoglobin).
4. A heart electrical tracing (ECG) to rule out a cardiac arrest.
5. Supplementary diagnostic procedures such as x-ray, ultrasound, or computed tomography scan.
6. An **endoscopy** – the non-invasive inspection of internal organs by use of a bendable tube that has a light and a video camera attached to the very end of it. It's important to note that the nomenclature of these structures change depending on which organ is being examined.

Pharmacological therapy for abdominal pain in individuals who suffer from the condition

The therapy will vary depending on the source of the discomfort but may involve the following:

1. Pain relief – Though medicines may not eliminate all discomfort, they should significantly reduce it..
2. Fluids – may get intravenous fluids to replenish lost fluids and rest the digestive system. Medications, such as those used to prevent nausea and vomiting.
3. Fasting – The doctor may advise you to avoid food and drink until the source of your discomfort has been determined.

Non-Pharmacological treatment

Most cases of stomach discomfort resolve without any extra care.

1. Apply a heating pad or a hot water bottle to the stomach.
2. Take a hot bath and relax. Avoid being burned by hot liquids.
3. Water and other clear drinks should be consumed in large quantities.
4. Consumption of caffeine- and alcohol-based pain relievers should be reduced.

Back pain:

It is estimated that back pain accounts for between 10% and 30% of all medical visits and lost workdays each year. Even if you don't take any precautions, you should be able to repair your back with some at-home care and work on improving your posture and physical conditioning in a matter of weeks and be back to normal in no time. Treating back pain surgically is an uncommon need.

Causes

Your doctor may be unable to pin down the origin of your back discomfort using diagnostic procedures:

- 1. Muscle or ligament strain.** Muscles and ligaments in the back may be strained or torn by Musculoskeletal injuries may be caused by the repeated lifting of large objects or by a sudden movement that is painful. These injuries can result in acute pain and discomfort that can linger for days or even weeks. If you are out of shape and don't take the essential precautions to protect your back, constant strain on your back may cause severe muscle spasms.
- 2. Bulging or ruptured disks.** The vertebrae in your spine are separated by disks, which function as cushions. Discs may put pressure on nerves if their delicate interiors rupture or expand. The back discomfort associated with a bulging or ruptured disk is not always present. X-rays of the spine are often performed for various reasons, and the discovery of disk disease is typically a fortunate side effect..

3.Arthritis. The low back is another common area to feel the effects of osteoarthritis. Spinal stenosis is characterized by a constriction of the canal space that surrounds the spinal cord. This condition is often caused by arthritis in the spine.

4.Osteoporosis.If your bones become porous and fragile, you may have osteoporosis, you run the risk of suffering from painful fractures in the vertebrae of your spine.

5. Certain meals may be off-limits based on the recommendations of your doctor.

6.Get some shut-eye.

7.If you're experiencing stomach ache, an antacid from the drugstore could assist.

8.Use paracetamol or other mild pain relievers. When it comes to dosing, be sure to double-check the packaging. Avoid pain relievers like aspirin unless your doctor specifically prescribes them. Some forms of stomach discomfort may be made worse by these medications.^[19].

Diagnosis

X-ray. These photos disclose the precise location of your bones, so you may use them to diagnose conditions like arthritis or a broken bone.^[20]

MRI or CT scans. A herniated disk, along with These scans have the capability of revealing disorders of the skeletal system, muscular system, connective tissues, nerves, ligaments, and blood vessels.

Blood tests. Using them, you may find out whether an infection or anything else is to blame for your discomfort.

Bone scan. The use of a bone scan to detect bone cancers or osteoporosis-related compression fractures is very uncommon yet possible..

Nerve studies. The electrical activity of your nerves and the resulting muscle contractions may be measured using electromyography (EMG). The presence of herniated disks or spinal canal constriction may be confirmed with this examination (spinal stenosis).

Pharmacological treatment:

Over-the-counter (OTC) pain relievers. Please follow your physician's instructions while using these drugs. The dangers of overuse are obvious. In the event that over-the-counter pain medications are ineffective. ^[21]

Muscle relaxants. A common side effect of muscle relaxants is drowsiness and lightheadedness.

Topical pain relievers. Pain relief may be applied directly to the skin using these items, which come in the form of creams, salves, ointments, or patches..

Narcotics. Opioid drugs like oxycodone and hydrocodone may be taken temporarily under a doctor's watchful eye. As opioids are ineffective against chronic pain, a typical prescription will only provide you with enough medication to last for a few days at most.

Antidepressants. Similar to amitriptyline, duloxetine (Cymbalta) and other tricyclic antidepressants are helpful in treating depression., have been demonstrated to alleviate persistent back pain independently of their impact on depression.

Non Pharmacological Treatment

It is possible to avoid or delay the onset of back discomfort by working on your fitness and being more aware of and observant of your body's mechanics..

Exercise. Strength and endurance in the back may be improved and muscle function enhanced with regular low-impact aerobic activity. Both swimming and walking are healthy options. Check with your physician before beginning any new physical activity.. ^[22]

Build muscle strength and flexibility.Exercises that focus on the abs and back strengthen the core, conditioning the abdominal and back muscles to operate in unison.

Don't let your weight get out of control. Overweight people often experience back pain. Weight loss may ease back discomfort for those who are overweight.

Quit smoking. A person's chance of experiencing low back discomfort rises if they smoke. Cigarette use is directly correlated with risk; hence, cutting down or stopping altogether should help lower the risk. [22]

Chest pain

Pain in the chest may be either sudden and intense, or gradually building up over time. The pressure or burning sensation in the chest might be excruciating at times. Sometimes the discomfort starts in the lower back or one or both arms and works its way up the back and into the jaw.

Symptoms

The origin of chest discomfort may result in a wide range of symptoms. Seeing a doctor is necessary since there is no foolproof method to know whether or not the reason is cardiac. [23]

Heart-related chest pain

Despite the common perception that heart illness causes chest pain, many persons with the condition report feeling a general achy all over instead. In general, one or more of the following may characterize or be linked with chest pain caused by a heart attack or other cardiac problem::

1. Feelings of fullness, tightness, burning, or pressure in the chest.
2. Pain that is crushing or scorching, and that travels to your back, neck, jaw, shoulders, and one or both arms.
3. Pain that last for more than a few minutes, intensifies with movement, fades and returns, or changes in severity. Shortness of breath
4. Cold sweats
5. Dizziness or weakness
6. Nausea or vomiting

Other types of chest pain

Chest discomfort from the heart might be hard to tell apart from other causes. However, the following conditions are more often linked to chest discomfort that is not related to a cardiac problem: [23]

1. Sourness, or the feeling that food is returning to your mouth.
2. Trouble swallowing.
3. Discomfort that improves or worsens with a shift in posture.
4. Breathing and coughing exacerbate the pain.
5. Discomfort at the slightest touch to the chest.
6. Persistent pain that lasts for many hours.

Causes

Many different things may cause chest discomfort, but they all need medical treatment.

Heart-related causes

Chest discomfort may have many different reasons, but some of the more common ones are heart-related:

Heart attack. A heart attack occurs when the heart's muscle stops receiving blood, as may happen if a blood clot formed..

Angina. The discomfort felt in the chest due to a lack of blood supply to the heart is known as angina. Plaque accumulation within the arteries leading to the heart is a common culprit in this situation. Plaques form in arteries and reduce blood flow, especially to the heart during exercise.

Aortic dissection. A blockage in the heart's main artery is potentially fatal (aorta). [23]

Sack-around-the-heart inflammation (pericarditis). Symptoms of this illness often include a stabbing pain that increases with breathing or resting in bed.

Digestive causes

Heartburn. When stomach acid travels up the esophagus and into the tube connecting the throat and stomach, it causes a painful, burning feeling just below the breastbone (esophagus).

Swallowing disorders. Esophageal disorders may force the person to swallow with difficulty or discomfort.

Causes of discomfort in the gallbladder and/or pancreatic. Pain in the upper abdomen and chest may originate in the digestive system and be caused by gallstones, gallbladder inflammation, or pancreatitis..

Muscle and bone causes

Injuries or other disorders affecting the structures of the chest wall, such as the heart, lungs, and ribs, may cause some forms of chest discomfort.:

Costochondritis. It's a painful inflammation of the rib cartilage, especially where the ribs attach to the breastbone..

Sore muscles. Fibromyalgia and other chronic pain disorders are associated with chronic muscle-related chest discomfort.

Injured ribs. Rib fractures and other rib injuries may lead to chest pain. [23]

Lung-related causes

Blood clot in the lung (pulmonary embolism).When a blood clot forms in a pulmonary artery, blood supply to the lungs is cut off..

Chronic inflammation of the lung's protective lining (pleurisy). Inhaling or coughing might aggravate the chest discomfort associated with this illness.

Collapsed lung. Symptoms of a collapsed lung include rapid onset of severe, persistent chest discomfort that may last for many hours, and difficulty breathing.

High blood pressure in the lung arteries (pulmonary hypertension). Chest discomfort is a symptom of this illness, which affects the arteries supplying blood to the lungs.

Other causes

It's important to rule out other potential causes of chest discomfort.:

Panic attack. Anxiety attacks are identified when the patient experiences intense fear together with other symptoms such as chest pain, rapid heart rate, quick breathing, profuse sweat, shortness of breath, nausea, dizziness, and a fear of dying..

Shingles.Pain and a ring of blisters that may reach from the back to the chest wall are two of the symptoms of shingles, which is caused by the reactivation of the chickenpox virus. [23]

Diagnostic tests

If your doctor suspects cardiac issues are to blame for your chest discomfort, he or she may prescribe diagnostic tests to rule them out.. These may include:

1.a chest X-ray, which examines your heart, lungs, and blood vessels; an electrocardiogram (ECG or EKG), which records the electrical activity of your heart; blood tests, which evaluate the amounts of enzymes in your blood; and an electrocardiogram, where the electrical activity of your heart is recorded.

2.an echocardiography is a kind of cardiac imaging test that records moving pictures by using sound waves. stress tests, which are used to monitor your heart function after you have exerted yourself, an MRI, which is used to search for damage to your heart or aorta, which is also used to look for damage to your heart. an angiography, which is performed to examine for blockages in particular arteries. [23]

Pharmacological treatment:

1. Medicines, such as nitroglycerin and other medications that open partly occluded arteries, clot-busting pharmaceuticals, or blood thinners, may be required in order to treat the condition.
2. Catheterization of the heart, which may entail the insertion of balloons or stents to free up clogged arteries, is performed.
3. Repairing the arteries surgically In certain cases, bypass surgery may also be referred to as coronary artery bypass grafting, is a procedure that may save a patient's life.

Treatments for other causes of chest pain include:

1. Lung reflation is necessary for collapsed lungs, and your physician will execute this procedure by inserting a chest tube or another equipment of a similar kind.
2. Antacids and other medications, as well as certain treatments, are used to treat the symptoms of acid reflux and heartburn.
3. Medication for anxiety disorders, such as antidepressants, is used to relieve chest discomfort brought on by panic episodes. [24]

Non Pharmacological treatment:

Hypnosis. Learning self-hypnosis, or other related mental methods such as meditation, neuro-feedback, or visualization, may assist in the reduction, control, and sometimes even elimination of some types of chest discomfort. [25]

Chronic pain:

In most cases, the duration of chronic pain ranges from months to years. As a result of changes in nerve function and transmission, there is no longer a correlation between the severity of the pain and the stimuli that are really causing it. The discomfort no longer serves a protective or warning role, and as a result, it is pointless. [Baumann, T.J et al. Pain Management.] [26]

Additionally, pain may be categorized as either nociceptive or neuropathic, depending on the source. [Widerström-Noga et al. International Spinal Cord Injury Pain Basic Data Set (version 2.0).] [27]

Figure: Chronic pain.

Types of chronic pain**Chronic Headaches**

According to a study, fifty percent of adults will report having headaches at some point throughout the course of a year, and more than ninety percent will report having had headaches at some point in their lives.

A headache is considered chronic if it occurs on average for at least fifteen days every single month during a period of at least three months in a row. The following are the most prevalent forms of persistent headaches:

1. Headaches induced by tension, which may be brought on by stress, exhaustion, or poor sleeping habits.
2. Headaches resulting from eye strain are brought on when the ocular muscles get stretched.
3. Migraines that are brought on by stimuli in the neurological system or by hormonal imbalances.
4. Headaches known as cluster headaches are brought on by an expansion of blood vessels in the brain.

What are the symptoms of chronic migraine?

Pain in the head that ranges from moderate to severe severity and is made worse by movement or activity that involves the body.

1. Pain on one or both sides of the head.
2. Throbbing pain or pressure-like pain.
3. Sensitivity to light,
4. sound,
5. smells.
6. Nausea/vomiting.
7. Dizziness. [28]

Non Pharmacological Treatment:

Avoid headache triggers. Keeping a headache journal might assist you in pinpointing the causes of your headaches so that you can steer clear of such causes in the future. Include specifics about each of your headaches, like when they started, what you were doing, and how long they lasted.

Avoid medication overuse. If you use medicine for your headaches more than twice a week, even over-the-counter medication, this might make your headaches worse and cause them to occur more often. In order to avoid potentially life-threatening complications, it is imperative that you discuss the process of tapering off the drug with your treating physician.

Get enough sleep. The recommended amount of sleep for an adult is seven to eight hours each night. It's essential to have a consistent schedule when it comes to when you go to bed and when you get up each day.

Don't skip meals. Consume healthy meals at around the same times every day. Avoid ingesting any foods or drinks, especially those that include caffeine, since they have the potential to bring on headaches. This includes chocolate and coffee. If you are overweight, you have to get serious about dropping the extra pounds.

Exercise regularly. Your physical and emotional well-being, as well as your ability to cope with stress, may benefit from engaging in aerobic physical exercise on a regular basis. After receiving clearance from your physician, choose activities that you take pleasure in doing, such as walking, swimming, or cycling. Take it easy at first to prevent hurting yourself.

Reduce stress. Stress is one of the most common factors that may lead to headaches that last for a long time. Put some effort into what you're doing. Streamline the things you do every day. Make sure you're ready. Maintain an upbeat and positive attitude. Exercising stress-relieving methods such as yoga, tai chi, or meditation, for instance, may be very beneficial.

Reduce caffeine. Caffeine is included in certain headache treatments because it has the potential to be helpful in lowering headache discomfort. However, caffeine also has the potential to make headaches worse. Make an effort to cut down on or get rid of caffeine completely in your diet. [28]

Pharmacological Treatment

Pain medications that are available over-the-counter often work effectively for treating occasional tension headaches. Be warned, however, that if you take these pills too often, you might end up with a headache that lasts all day every day.

Your healthcare professional may suggest using prescription headache medication for headaches that are severe or occur often. An oncoming migraine may be treated with triptans and several other sorts of medications. You take them as soon as you feel the beginnings of a headache coming on.

There is some evidence that treatments for high blood pressure, epilepsy, and depression may help avoid migraines. Your doctor may suggest that you give one of these medicines a try in order to lessen the severity and frequency of your headaches [28]

Chronic Joint Pain

Types of Chronic Pain experienced by people in the United States is discomfort in the joints. This sort of pain may be brought on by trauma, infection, or just the natural aging process.

Some of the more common types of chronic joint pain are:

1. Degeneration of the joints is the hallmark of osteoarthritis that often affects the bigger joints and is associated with advanced age.
2. Rheumatoid arthritis is a kind of arthritis that is caused by an autoimmune condition that leads to swelling of the joint spaces.
3. Injuries caused by repeated motion are quite frequent among sportsmen and other persons who engage in physically demanding activities on a regular basis.
4. Bursitis is an inflammation that occurs when the fluid-filled sacs that cushion the joints become swollen.
5. The inflammation of joint tendons may lead to a condition known as tendinitis.

The symptoms of joint pain:

1. Swelling.
2. Stiff or swollen joint.
3. Numbness.
4. Joints that make noise as they are moved, such as clicking, grinding, or cracking noises when the joint is moved.
5. Painful movement.
6. Having trouble bending or straightening the joint is difficult. a cessation of motion [29]

The causes joint pain:

Osteoarthritis, The degeneration of cartilage, the protective cushion that sits in between bones, may increase the risk of developing a common type of arthritis throughout a person's lifetime. This is a particularly worrisome development since the repetitive stress placed on our joints by the activities of daily life may, over the course of a person's lifetime, cause a type of arthritis that is rather prevalent. The joints hurt and become stiff as the condition progresses. Osteoarthritis is a degenerative joint disease that advances gradually and often presents itself in middle age. It is most common in those over the age of 50.

Rheumatoid arthritis is a condition that lasts for a long time and affects the joints, making them swell and hurt.

Gout is a painful disorder that occurs when crystals from the body aggregate in the joint, causing the joint to enlarge and cause significant pain. This often takes place in the great toe.

Bursitis is a result of excessive usage. The shoulder, hip, knee, or elbow are the most common locations to discover it.

Injuries, injuries such as sprains and shattered bones.

Tendinitis tendonitis refers to inflammation of the tendons, which are the elastic bands that connect bone and muscle. Tendons are the flexible bands that link bone and muscle. Overuse is the most common cause of this condition, which manifests most often in the shoulder, elbow, or heel. [29]

Pharmacological Treatment:

Although there may not be a treatment that would permanently eliminate the patient's discomfort, it may be controlled to provide some degree of relief. Taking over-the-counter medicine or engaging in straightforward physical activity may, sometimes, alleviate the discomfort experienced. On the other hand, the discomfort may be an indication of a condition that can only be remedied via the use of a certain drug or through surgery.

Acetaminophen, often known as Tylenol®, or other nonsteroidal anti-inflammatory medications (ibuprofen)

may be able to assist relieve the discomfort. These two medications may be purchased without a prescription at local pharmacies; however, your healthcare provider may prescribe a higher dosage for you.

Topical treatments, Pain relief medications, such as ointments or gels that may be massaged into the skin over the region of the joint that is afflicted, may also be helpful. Some of them are available over-the-counter, while others require a prescription from your primary care physician.

Dietary supplements, like glucosamine, may help alleviate discomfort. Before using any over-the-counter supplements, be sure to see your physician. Even though they haven't been verified by science, some people find that using natural therapies like glucosamine helps them feel better while they're dealing with pain. [29]

Antidepressants a patient who suffers from joint discomfort may be administered in order to aid enhance their ability to sleep..

Steroids, Pain and swelling are temporarily alleviated by medications that are often administered through injection into the affected joint.

Painkilling drugs that help ease pain.

Non Pharmacological Treatment:

Physical or Occupational Therapy, in conjunction with a well-rounded exercise regimen, may gradually help alleviate discomfort and increase flexibility.

Supportive aids, Supporting the joint using an external or internal device can make mobility easier. The physician, whether for a physical or

A social worker or occupational therapist will be able to guide you toward the appropriate choice(s) from the options that are available.

Weight loss may also be advised, depending on the circumstances, to reduce the amount of stress placed on the joints.

Simple at-home treatments, Some treatments, such as rubbing the afflicted region for brief intervals many times each day, may be indicated as possible treatments. Taking a relaxing soak in a warm bathtub could also provide some help.

Exercise may assist in regaining lost strength and function. The finest aerobic exercises are those that have little impact, such as walking and swimming. Those who regularly engage in hard exercises or sports activities may find that they need to modify their routines or switch to ones that have less effect on the body. Stretching your muscles gently with exercises might also be of use. Consult your primary care provider before starting or continuing any kind of fitness regimen. [29]

Muscle Pain**Causes of muscle pain**

Stress, tension, or even physical exertion might be the culprit behind aching muscles. There are a number of medical diseases that are known to cause muscular discomfort.. [Treede, R. et al. 2017, A classification of chronic pain for ICD- 11.], [Katz J, Rosenbloom BN. 2015, The golden anniversary of Melzack and Wall's gate control theory of pain] [30]

- Infections
- Hyper or hypo-thyroidism
- Hypokalemia
- Autoimmune conditions e.g. lupus
- Side effects of certain medications (i.e. the Statins)

Figure: Muscle Pain

Pathophysiology of muscle pain

Pain in the muscle may be generated by the activation of nociceptors in the muscle, which may be brought on by overuse of the muscle, inflammation, or even injury to the muscle itself physically. Endogenous substances are created as a response to wounded tissues or nociceptor nerve endings after an impact. This occurs as a result of the impact. This can occur when the tissues have sustained severe injury or when the nociceptor nerve terminals have been subjected to intense, damaging stimulation. The compounds bradykinin, histamine, serotonin, prostaglandins, and potassium ions are some examples of those that are produced when there is an injury. Other molecules that are released include potassium ions. [Butts, R., Dunning, et al. 2016, 'Peripheral and Spinal Mechanisms of Pain and Dry Needling Mediated Analgesia'] [31]

1. Potassium ion
2. Prostaglandin
3. E2 Bradykinin
4. Serotonin
5. Somatostatin
6. Adenosine
7. triphosphate

[Butts, R., Dunning, et al. 2016, 'Peripheral and Spinal Mechanisms of Pain and Dry Needling Mediated Analgesia], [Mense, S. 2008. mechanisms and clinical significance.] [31], [32]

In cases of muscular inflammation, there is a rise in the levels of substance P and nerve growth factor (NGF). This, in turn, leads to hyperalgesia, which is an enhanced sensitivity to painful stimuli in the muscle that is afflicted. Muscle discomfort may come in a variety of forms, the most common of which are sprains and strains, which are particularly prevalent among the elderly. When the ligaments are stretched beyond their normal range of motion, the outcome is a sprain. Joints that have been twisted might give rise to this issue. Ankles and wrists are the portions of the body that are most often affected by this condition. After this, patients will often experience discomfort, swelling, and perhaps bruising. On the other hand, strains occur when a muscle or tendon is stretched beyond its normal range of motion.

Diagnosis

Physical Examination

Your doctor or another medical professional may perform a physical examination on you and push on various muscles to check for discomfort and soreness (including trigger points). They could also look for symptoms of edema, warmth, redness, or discoloration on the skin and the surrounding tissue.

Blood and Urine Tests

The diagnosis of some conditions that cause muscular discomfort may benefit from the use of blood testing. These include the erythrocyte sedimentation rate (ESR) and C-reactive protein (CRP) tests, which both look for inflammation, which can be a sign of a number of diseases and infections.

Pain in the muscle may be generated by the activation of nociceptors in the muscle, which may be brought on by overuse of the muscle, inflammation, or even injury to the muscle itself physically. Endogenous substances are created as a response to wounded tissues or nociceptor nerve endings after an impact. This occurs as a result of the impact. This can occur when the tissues have sustained severe injury or when the nociceptor nerve terminals have been subjected to intense, damaging stimulation. The compounds bradykinin, histamine, serotonin, prostaglandins, and potassium ions are some examples of those that are produced when there is an injury. Other molecules that are released include potassium ions.

Thyroid function tests can also be used to diagnose thyroid disorders.

Urinalysis is another common way to find out if a person has rhabdomyolysis because it looks for waste products and toxins in the urine.

Imaging

Imaging studies may also help narrow down the potential causes of muscle discomfort to a more manageable level. Your healthcare professional may also use them to screen for abnormal growths.

The following imaging studies are some of the options for diagnosing muscle pain::

- **Ultrasound:** A diagnostic imaging procedure that employs sound waves in order to provide detailed pictures of the patient's interior tissues. Sonography and ultrasound imaging are both types of the same imaging test that use sound waves to provide precise pictures of inside structures. Ultrasound imaging is also known as ultrasound scanning.
- **Computed tomography (CT):** The field of medical imaging has been completely transformed by the development of a method that takes several X-ray pictures and uses them to produce three-dimensional "slices" of interior structures.
- **Magnetic resonance imaging (MRI):** imaging technique that creates detailed pictures of soft tissues by using strong magnetic and radio waves to make the images. Magnetic resonance imaging, sometimes known as MRI, is a cutting-edge imaging technique that creates photographs of soft tissues (such the brain and spine) that are extraordinarily detailed because to the innovative combination of strong magnetic fields and radio waves. [33]

Treatment

Your healthcare practitioner will develop a treatment plan for you after the underlying cause of your muscle pain has been identified. This plan will address both the symptomatic muscle pain as well as the root of the problem..

Self-Care Strategies/Non Pharmacological treatment:

- **Rest:** Take as much time off as you can to rest the damaged muscle and give the inflammation time to go down.
- **Ice:** A cold compress should be applied to the muscle for three to four sessions of fifteen minutes each every four to six hours.
- **Compression:** You may alleviate the discomfort and swelling in your muscle by wrapping it in an elastic bandage.
- **Elevation:** While you are recovering, keep the damaged muscle elevated above the level of your heart.

[33]

Pharmacological treatment:**Medications**

Your primary care physician or other healthcare professional may recommend that you take a variety of drugs in order to address the underlying condition that is causing the muscular discomfort.

Nonsteroidal Anti-Inflammatory (NSAIDs)

Nonsteroidal anti-inflammatory drugs (NSAIDs) like Aleve (naproxen) and Advil (ibuprofen) can help with muscle strains and myofascial pain syndrome. However, these drugs can sometimes cause unpleasant side effects like nausea, heartburn, and stomach pain.

Muscle Relaxants

Although muscle relaxants like Flexural (cyclobenzaprine) and Zanaflex (tizanidine) may give temporary relief from the discomfort associated with a temporary muscular injury, they are not intended to treat persistent or chronic pain.

Antidepressants

Myofascial pain syndrome, fibromyalgia, and chronic fatigue syndrome are sometimes treated with tricyclic antidepressants like Elavil (amitriptyline). Other medications include physical therapy and lifestyle changes.

In the event that a tricyclic antidepressant is not well accepted, other classes of antidepressants, such as Cymbalta (duloxetine), may be substituted for its use in the treatment of myofascial pain syndrome and fibromyalgia.

Corticosteroids

There are a variety of inflammatory disorders that may be treated with corticosteroids (also known as steroids), including polymyalgia rheumatica and inflammatory myopathies. Having said that, the sustained suppression of the immune system that may result from using steroids like prednisone for an extended period of time can lead to a number of major adverse consequences. There are additional medications that spare the body's supply of steroids, such as methotrexate, which has the ability to decrease inflammation and may be safer for usage over the long term.

Vitamin Supplements

- Osteomalacia is often treated with vitamin D supplements that are prescribed by a doctor in order to slow down the breakdown of bone minerals. In addition to that, you will be urged to consume foods that are rich in vitamin D.

Anti-Infectives

- If you have been diagnosed with a bacterial illness such as pyomyositis, you will probably need to take antibiotics in order to get rid of the infection. Other possible reasons include viral infections, fungal infections, or parasitic infections, each of which calls for a different class of medication.. [33]

Methodology

- The primary data has been collected by a survey that was collected among several peoples who were suffering from pain problem and took necessary steps.
- Secondary data has been collected by researching articles, author's publications, web portals, websites and Wikipedia.

I gone through to many articles, websites to find my desire information. It helped me a lot to gather all information about Pain management and its treatment.

Conclusion

The effective management of pain is essential to achieving a higher quality of life. People who are in pain are unable to participate in activities that they like. It may inhibit them from communicating with others and from socializing in general. It has the potential to influence both their state of mind and their cognitive functioning. The research, diagnosis, and treatment of pain are the three primary focuses of pain management, which is a medical strategy that draws from a variety of scientific and alternative healing modalities. The order in which acute pain management goals are prioritized can differ from practice to practice. The following are some of the categories that may be used to classify the pharmaceuticals that are used most frequently: Non-steroidal anti-inflammatory drugs and acetaminophen: There are

2020;368:m791.

21. Neural Plasticity and Disorders of the Nervous System. Cambridge University Press. Pain 2006. pp. 149–240.

22. <https://www.fairview.org/patient-education/41117>

23. <https://www.verywellhealth.com/conditions-most-often-associated-with-chronic-pain->

24. Hecke O van, Torrance N, Smith BH. Chronic pain epidemiology and its clinical relevance. Br J Anaesth. 2013 Jan 7;111(1):13–8.

25. <https://my.clevelandclinic.org/health/diseases/9638-chronic-migraine>

26. Baumann, T.J., Herndon, C.M., Strickland, J.M. Chapter 44. Pain Management. In: DiPiro

JT, Talbert RL, Yee GC, Matzke GR, Wells BG, Posey L. eds. Pharmacotherapy: A Pathophysiologic Approach, 9e. New York, NY: McGraw-Hill; <http://accesspharmacy.mhmedical.com/content.aspx?bookid=689&Sectionid=45310494>. (Accessed: January 13, 2017)

27. Widerström-Noga, E., Biering-Sørensen, F., Bryce, T., Cardenas, D., Finnerup, N., Jensen, M., Richards, J. and Siddall, P. (2014). The International Spinal Cord Injury Pain Basic Data Set (version 2.0). Spinal Cord 2014; 52, pp.282–286.

28. Goldberg DS, McGee SJ. Pain as a global public health priority. BMC Public Health. 2011;11:770.

29. <https://my.clevelandclinic.org/health/diseases/9638-chronic-migraine>

30. Treede, R., Rief, W., Barke, A., Aziz, Q., Bennett, M.I., Benoliel, R., Cohen, M., Evers, S., Finnerup, N.B., First, M.B., Giamberardino, M.A., Kaasa, S., Kosek, E., Lavand'homme, P., Nicholas, M., Perrot, S., Scholz, J., Schug, S., Smith, B.H., Svensson, P., Vlaeyen, J.W.S. & Wang, S. 2015. A classification of chronic pain for ICD-11. <https://www.ncbi.nlm.nih.gov/pmc/articles/PMC4450869/> (Accessed: 13 January 2017).

31. Butts, R., Dunning, J., Perreault, T., Mourad, F. and Matthew, G. 2016. 'Peripheral and Spinal Mechanisms of Pain and Dry Needling Mediated Analgesia: A Clinical Resource Guide for Health Care Professionals, International Journal of Physical Medicine & Access/peripheral-and-spinal-mechanisms-of-pain-and-dry-needling-mediated-analgesia-a-clinical-resource-guide-for-health-care-professional-2329-9096-1000327.php?aid=71582 (Accessed: 13 January 2016).

32. Mense, S. 2008. Muscle pain: mechanisms and clinical significance. NCBI, 105(12), pp 214-219 [Online]. Available at: <https://www.ncbi.nlm.nih.gov/pmc/articles/PMC2696782/>. (Accessed: 13 January 2016).

33. Katz J, Rosenbloom BN. The golden anniversary of Melzack and Wall's gate control theory of pain: Celebrating 50 years of pain research and management. Pain Res Manag 2015;20, pp.285- 286.

34. <https://my.clevelandclinic.org/health/diseases/9638-chronic-migraine>

35. <https://my.clevelandclinic.org/health/diseases/9639-headaches>

36. <https://www.healthline.com/health/chest-pain#treatment>

37. <https://www.mayoclinic.org/diseases-conditions/chest-pain/symptoms-causes/syc-20370838>

38. <https://www.fairview.org/patient-education/41117>

39. <https://www.spine-health.com/glossary/pain-management/pain-medicine>

40. <https://www.ncbi.nlm.nih.gov/pmc/articles/PMC5796556/>

41. <https://thepainmanagementgroup.com/behavioral-health/goal-setting-for-chronic-pain-patients/>

Dr. S M Mahamudul Hassan Rizvi*,

¹Department of Orthopedic Trauma and Microsurgery, Zhongnan Hospital of Wuhan University, Wuhan 430071, China. .

Dr. Shengxiang Tao²

²Department of Orthopedic Trauma and Microsurgery, Zhongnan Hospital of Wuhan University, Wuhan 430071,China.

Dr.Xiang Hu³,

³Department of Orthopedic Trauma and Microsurgery, Zhongnan Hospital of Wuhan University, Wuhan 430071,China.

Dr.Liu Hui⁴

⁴Department of Orthopedic Trauma and Microsurgery, Zhongnan Hospital of Wuhan University, Wuhan 430071,China.

Dr.Shami.Aihemaiti⁵

⁵Department of Orthopedic Trauma and Microsurgery, Zhongnan Hospital of Wuhan University, Wuhan 430071,China.